

The influence of work behavior, integrity and organizational climate on police performance of personnel in the medical and health sector

Agusta Lopez Ade, Yusuf Montundu, Laode Asfahyadin Aliddin, Ibnu Hajar, Sri Wiyati Mahrani and Nursaban Rommy Suleman *

Department of Management, Faculty of Economics and Business, Halu Oleo University Kendari, Indonesia.

World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 2022, 16(02), 101–108

Publication history: Received on 13 September 2022; revised on 16 October 2022; accepted on 19 October 2022

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2022.16.2.1072>

Abstract

This study aims to examine or analyze the effect of work behavior, integrity and organizational climate on the performance of personnel in the medical and health sector. This research is a quantitative approach. The population in this study was personnel in the medical and health sector with a sample of 51 people. The analysis used multiple linear regression analysis with the help of IBM SPSS 22 Software. The results of the study showed that (1) work behavior had a positive and significant effect on the performance of personnel in the medical and health sector, (2) the integrity of personnel in the medical and health sector, and (3) the organizational climate had a positive and significant effect on the performance of personnel in the medical and health sector. (4) Simultaneously work behavior, integrity and organizational climate have a positive and significant impact on the performance of personnel in the medical and health sector.

Keywords: Work behavior; Integrity; Organizational climate; Performance

1. Introduction

The existence of human resources plays a very important role in the company. Employees as motivated human resources will carry out activities or tasks as well as possible so that they can provide maximum work results. Companies and employees are two things that need each other. If employees work well and succeed in bringing progress to the company, the benefits obtained will be reaped by both parties. So that employees can continue to work to meet their needs, while the company can maintain its existence and growth

According to (1), human resources are one of the main capital in an organization, which can make an invaluable contribution to the strategy for achieving organizational goals. One example of the importance of the contribution of human resources in a company can be seen from the production process. Where when the company already has strong finances, fulfilled raw materials, and the latest technology but lacks good human resources, the production process will not run smoothly. According to (2) human resources is the science and art that regulates the relationship and role of the workforce to be effective and efficient in helping the realization of the goals of the company, employees, and society.

Work behavior is a very important part of the work life of the organization, work behavior is the actions and attitudes shown by people who work. According to (4) work ability behavior and behaviors where it is very important in every job or work situation. Behavior is the process of how someone does it. Behavior is an element that is central to human differences. In work, without behavior there can be no production. Therefore they must be nurtured and given a

* Corresponding author: Nursaban

Department of Management, Faculty of Economics and Business, Halu Oleo University Kendari, Indonesia.

motivation. While work behavior according to (5) is how people in the work environment can actualize themselves through attitudes at work.

Research conducted by (6), (7), (8), (9), the results of the study show that work behavior has a positive and significant effect on performance. While the research conducted by (10) The Influence of Work Environment and Work Behavior on Employee Performance.

In addition to work behavior, integrity is the most important in an organization. According to (11), integrity is an element of character that underlies the emergence of professional recognition. Integrity is a quality that underlies public trust and is a benchmark for members in testing all decisions they make. professional recognition . (12) Integrity is supported by 6 pillars of character consisting of honesty, justice, wisdom, frugality, and responsibility. Integrity is expected to lead to a common goal to achieve the aspired. As in a company, integrity is very important. Without integrity, people will be lazy to do what is their duty because they do everything because they have to, not out of their conscience. If the lack of integrity in individuals really occurs, then individual efforts in improving the company's goals will be difficult to achieve. Research conducted by (13), (14), (15), (16), (17), (18), The results of the study show that integrity has a positive and significant effect on performance (13).

In addition to work behavior and integrity, there is also an organizational climate that is no less important in supporting performance. According to (19), organizational climate is a concept that describes the internal atmosphere of the organizational environment felt by its members during their activities in order to achieve organizational goals. According to (20), states that organizational climate is the perception of organizational members (individually or in groups) and those who are in constant contact with the organization about what is or is happening in the organization's internal environment on a regular basis, which affects organizational attitudes and behavior and organizational member performance. which then determines organizational performance. (21) argues that organizational climate is the relative environmental quality of an organization experienced by its members, where it has an effect on their behavior and how the organization functions well. Organizational climate is divided into two, namely organizational environmental conditions involving physical and organizational environmental conditions involving psychological or non-physical aspects. Research conducted by (22), (23), (24), (25), (26), (27), the results of the study show that organizational climate has a positive and significant effect on performance.

2. Literature Review and Hypothesis Development

2.1 Work Behavior

Work behavior is a very important part of the work life of the organization, work behavior is the actions and attitudes shown by people who work. According to (3) work ability behavior and behaviors where it is very important in every job or work situation. Behavior is the process of how someone does it. Behavior is an element that is central to human differences. In work, without behavior there can be no production.

According to (28), behavior is anything that a person does talking to superiors, typing letters, keeping records, serving customers and so on that shows a person's behavior (behavior). To understand how individuals behave in organizations, a manager must know why there are differences in behavior among employees. according to (29), concluded that there are four indicators of work behavior, namely:

- Social relationships,
- Vocational skills,
- Work motivation,
- Initiative— confidence

There are four indicators that can be used to determine work behavior according to (29), namely:

- Social relationships

A worker must have good social relations with other workers , where each worker must supervise colleagues so that they act in the right way and warn if there are mistakes.

- Vocational skills

The skills that a person has according to his job, for example someone with cooking skills is suitable to be a Chef.

- work motivation

There is a willingness to work to achieve certain goals such as physiological needs, security, love, self-esteem, and self-actualization.

- Initiative—confidence

Namely, good work behavior must foster full confidence and take the initiative that all work can be carried out in accordance with the existing job description.

2.2 Integrity

According to (11), integrity is an element of character that underlies the emergence of professional recognition. Integrity is a quality that underlies public trust and is a benchmark for members in testing all decisions they make. Integrity is often understood in the context of behavior, and integrity behavior is generally understood in terms of ethics and morals. The principle of integrity requires every practitioner to be firm, honest, and fair in their professional and business relationships (30). Integrity is a quality that underlies public trust and is a benchmark for members to test all of their decisions. Integrity requires a person to be honest and transparent, courageous, wise, and responsible for carrying out his work. These four elements are needed to build trust and provide the basis for reliable decision making.

Meanwhile, according to (31) states that integrity strengthens trust and therefore becomes the basis for evaluating their performance, but integrity is an element of character that underlies the emergence of professional recognition. According to (32), integrity can accept unintentional mistakes and honest differences of opinion but cannot accept fraud or a violation of principles. In the face of rules, standards, special guidelines or facing conflicting opinions, members must examine their decisions or actions by asking whether members have done what they should have done and whether members have maintained their integrity. Where integrity requires its members to comply with technical and ethical standards. It also requires members to follow the principles of objectivity and professional prudence.

Indicators of integrity according to (11), which are as follows:

- Honest

Honesty is the attitude or nature of the auditor who states something really and as it is, neither added nor subtracted. While transparency or transparency is the nature of openness which means that decisions are taken and their implementation is carried out in a way or mechanism that follows the rules or regulations set by the institution.

- Brave

Courage means having a steady heart, not being afraid and having great confidence in facing the dangers of adversity.

- Wise

Is an assessment of a thought, word and deed based on the surrounding scope by not imposing the will on anything and anyone.

- Responsible

In carrying out responsibility means having an obligation to bear and bear the responsibility in carrying out tasks.

2.3 Organizational Climate

By (33) states that organizational climate is organizational climate which is an internal environment or organizational psychology can also be seen as being able to influence the behavior of the members in it and the organizational climate is formed because of the activities in an organization. (34) states that organizational climate is the quality of every interaction process within an organization to be able to achieve the goals that have been set so that employees will make assessments about the company and form perceptions in themselves about the organizational climate where they work. According to (19), organizational climate is a concept that describes the internal atmosphere of the organizational environment felt by its members during their activities in order to achieve organizational goals.

By (35) states that organizational climate is organizational climate which is an internal environment or organizational psychology can also be seen as being able to influence the behavior of the members in it and the organizational climate is formed due to activities in an organization. (34) states that organizational climate is the quality of every interaction process within an organization to be able to achieve the goals that have been set so that employees will make assessments about the company and form perceptions in themselves about the organizational climate where they work. According to (19), organizational climate is a concept that describes the internal atmosphere of the organizational environment felt by its members during their activities in order to achieve organizational goals.

By (36) states that climate is a shared perception or perception of organizational policies, implementation of policies and procedures, both formal and informal. Climate as a representation of organizational goals and objectives and the tools and means that are imitated and implemented to achieve the desired results.

By (19), organizational climate has organizational elements that become benchmarks in measuring organizational climate, namely:

- Leadership Quality

Namely the ability to influence, move and direct an action on a person or group to achieve certain goals that are practiced by leaders towards their employees.

- Trust

Namely the trust given by the leadership to its employees in carrying out work in the company.

- Communication

Namely the process of transferring information and understanding from communication up, down, to the side in an organization.

- Responsibility

Namely the attitude that exists in the leadership and employees towards the ownership of the company and the tasks performed.

- Fair remuneration, namely wages given to employees according to their expectations, namely the work produced, skills and community wage standards.

- Opportunity

That is an opportunity given by employees to improve their work performance.

- Control

That is an action taken by the leadership so that the company or organization is well controlled so that it does not suffer losses

2.4 Performance

According to (37), states that Human Resource Management (HRM) is: "The process of human management, through planning, recruitment, selection, training, development, compensation, career, safety and health as well as maintaining industrial relations until termination of employment in order to achieve company goals and increase stakeholder welfare. According to (38)states that "Human resource management, abbreviated as HRM, is a science or method of how to manage the relationship and role of resources (labor) owned by individuals efficiently and effectively and can be used optimally so that the company's common goals are achieved, employees and society to the maximum".

Personnel performance is the result of work in quality and quantity achieved by a personnel in carrying out their duties in accordance with the responsibilities that have been given to them (39). In addition, according to (40)Human Resource Management (HRM) is the activity of planning, procuring, developing, maintaining, and using human resources to achieve goals both individually and in organizations. According to (2)human resource management is "the science and art of managing the relationship and the role of the workforce to be effective and efficient in helping the realization of the goals of the company, employees, and society.

According to (41), performance is a general term used in part or all of the actions or activities of an organization in a period with a reference to a number of standards such as projected past costs on the basis of efficiency, management responsibility or accountability and the like.

Performance indicators refer to (42)regarding the performance assessment of members of the State police

- Leadership

Able to manage organizational resource management well.

- Service orientation

Complete tasks as well as possible with a polite attitude both internally and externally.

- Communication

Convey information from various means so that it becomes clear and easy to understand

- Emotional control

Manage yourself to face difficult problems, criticism or when working under pressure with a positive attitude.

- Integrity

Carry out duties by being honest, sincere, and never abusing authority and daring to take the risk from his actions

- Empathy

Listen and understand other people's thoughts, feelings, or problems that are not spoken or not fully conveyed and always act proactively to make changes, and be kind to the surrounding environment.

- Commitment to Organization

Align personal behavior with the interests of the organization in order to realize the vision and mission

- Initiative

Act more than the demands of his position without waiting for orders with the aim of improving / improving work results that do not conflict with work procedures.

- Discipline

Be present on time at the apple ceremony and comply with the applicable laws and regulations and/or official regulations with a sense of responsibility and always comply with the provisions of working hours.

- Cooperation

Able to cooperate with colleagues, superiors, subordinates both inside and outside the Polri organization and respect and accept the opinions of others, willing to accept decisions taken legally which have become joint decisions

From the literature review. The conceptual framework of this study is shown below:

Figure 1 Research Conceptual Framework

Hypothesis is as follow:

H1 : Work behavior, integrity and organizational climate have a positive and significant effect simultaneously on Police performance

H2: Work behavior has a positive and significant effect on Police performance

H3 : Integrity has a positive and significant effect on police performance

H4: Organizational climate has a positive and significant effect on Police performance

3. Methods

The object of research in this research is Biddokkes personnel of the Southeast Sulawesi Regional Police. The time period for the implementation of this research is approximately 45 days. Population is a generalization consisting of subject objects that have certain qualities and characteristics that are determined by researchers to be studied and then drawn conclusions (Sugiyono, 2008: 80). The population in this study was the North Sulawesi Regional Police Biddokes Personnel as many as 51 people and all of them were used as respondents or in the census. The unit of analysis of this research is the individual, because it reflects the response of the research subjects individually. The sampling technique used is random based on strata (*stratified proportional random sampling*), which is to first classify the population into sub-populations according to the status of members of the National Police (rank/class). This study uses a questionnaire as a data collection instrument with the available answer choices in the form of a Likert Scale score from 1 to 5 intervals, 1 indicates strongly disagree and 5 indicates strongly agrees. This research data was tested using SPSS version 22 software.

4. Results and discussion

In this study, the data analysis technique used is multiple linear regression which examines the effect of work behavior (X1), integrity (X2), organizational climate (X3), and personnel performance (Y) variables.

Based on the results of data processing as described in table 5.13, a regression equation for work behavior (X1), integrity (X2), organizational climate (X3), and personnel performance (Y) can be formed as follows:

$$Y = 0.318X_1 + 0.383X_2 + 0.324X_3$$

The regression coefficient of the estimation results in the equation above, all independent variables have a positive coefficient, meaning that work behavior (X1), integrity (X2), organizational climate (X3), and Personnel Performance

(Y) that if work behavior is good, it will improve personnel performance, as well as the variables of integrity and organizational climate that if good, the performance of personnel will increase the performance of Biddokkes Polda Sultra personnel.

Table 1 Results of multiple linear regression analysis

Influence between variables	Standardized Coefficients	T-value	Sig-t	Results
Work behavior→ Performance	0.318	3,024	0.004	Received
integrity → Performance	0.383	3,675	0.001	Received
Organization ➔ climate Performance	0.324	3.085	0.003	Received
R = 0.741 R square = 0.549 SEE = 3,003	F value = 19,093 Sig. F = 0.000 N = 51			

Data source processed 2022

4.1 Partial Test

In the partial significant test, each of the effects of work behavior, integrity and organizational climate will be partially tested positive and significant on the performance of Biddokkes Polda Sultra personnel, as follows:

4.1.1 The Influence of Work Behavior on Personnel Performance

The results of testing the effect of work behavior on personnel performance can be proven by the estimated value of the Beta coefficient of 0.318 in a positive direction. The path coefficient is positive, meaning that the influence of work behavior on personnel performance is unidirectional. This result is also supported by a probability value (*p-value*) of $0.004 < 0.05$. The results of hypothesis testing prove that work behavior has a positive and significant effect on personnel performance. This means that work behavior is unidirectional and significant to personnel performance, so the proposed hypothesis (H1) is accepted.

4.1.2 Effect of Integrity on Personnel Performance

The results of testing the effect of integrity on personnel performance can be proven by the estimated value of the Beta coefficient of 0.383 in a positive direction. The path coefficient is positive, meaning that the influence of integrity on personnel performance is unidirectional. This result is also supported by a probability value (*p-value*) of $0.001 < 0.05$. The results of hypothesis testing prove that integrity has a positive and significant effect on personnel performance. This means that integrity is unidirectional and significant to the performance of personnel, so that the proposed hypothesis (H2) is accepted.

4.1.3 The Effect of Organizational Climate on Personnel Performance

The results of testing the influence of organizational climate on personnel performance can be proven by the estimated value of the Beta coefficient of 0.324 in a positive direction. The path coefficient is positive, meaning that the influence of organizational climate on personnel performance is unidirectional. This result is also supported by a probability value (*p-value*) of $0.003 < 0.05$. The results of hypothesis testing prove that organizational climate has a positive and significant effect on personnel performance. This means that the organizational climate is unidirectional and significant to the performance of personnel, so that the proposed hypothesis (H3) is accepted.

5. Conclusion

Based on the results and discussion in this study, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- Work behavior has a positive and significant impact on the performance of Biddokkes Polda Sultra personnel. So that the better the work behavior of the Southeast Sulawesi Regional Police Biddokkes personnel will have an impact on increasing the performance of the Southeast Sulawesi Regional Police Biddokkes personnel.
- Integrity has a positive and significant impact on the performance of the North Sulawesi Regional Police Biddokkes personnel. So that the better the integrity of the personnel of the Biddokkes Polda Sultra will have an impact on improving the performance of the Biddokkes personnel of the Polda Sultra.

- climate has a positive and significant influence on the performance of the personnel of the Southeast Sulawesi Regional Police Biddokkes. So that the better the organizational climate, the better the performance of Biddokkes Polda Sultra personnel
- Simultaneously work behavior, integrity and organizational climate have a positive and significant impact on the performance of Biddokkes Polda Sultra personnel

Compliance with ethical standards

Acknowledgments

The author would like to thank all elements involved who helped in the data collection procedure.

Disclosure of conflict of interest

There is no conflict of interest.

References

- [1] Noor S. Penerapan Analisis Swot dalam Menentukan Strategi Pemasaran Daihatsu Luxio di Malang. J INTEKNA. 2014;14(2):102–209.
- [2] Hasibuan, M. S., & Hasibuan HMS. Manajemen sumber daya manusia. Bumi Aksara; 2016.
- [3] Manullang M dan Marihot Manulang. Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia Bagian Penerbitan. Yogyakarta: Fakultas Ekonomi Universitas Gajah Mada; 2010.
- [4] Manullang, M., & Manulang M. Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia. Bagian Penerbitan Fakultas Ekonomi Universitas Gajah Mada; 2010.
- [5] Robbins PS. Prinsip-Prinsip Perilaku Organisasi. Edisi Keli. 2002.
- [6] Manampiring B, Soegoto CKAS, Budaya P, Dan O, Kerja P, Kinerja T. Pengaruh Budaya Organisasi Dan Perilaku Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan Di Balai Pelestarian Nilai Budaya Sulawesi Utara. J EMBA J Ris Ekon Manajemen, Bisnis dan Akunt. 2019;7(3):4026–35.
- [7] Sunaryo S. Pengaruh Perubahan Organisasi, Budaya Organisasi Dan Perilaku Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan Di PT. Sisirau Medan. J Ilm Manaj dan Bisnis. 2017;18(1):101–14.
- [8] Wibowo TS, Badi'ati AQ, Annisa AA, Wahab MKA, Jamaludin MR, Rozikan M, et al. Effect of Hard Skills, Soft Skills, Organizational Learning and Innovation Capability on Islamic University Lecturers' Performance. Syst Rev Pharm. 2020;11(7):556–69.
- [9] Bayu AH. PENGARUH KETERAMPILAN KERJA, DAN PERILAKU KERJA TERHADAP KINERJA PEGAWAI KANTOR BEA CUKAI YOGYAKARTA. Dr Diss Univ Widya Dharma Klaten. 2021;
- [10] Wisna Wardani Sidik, Samdin DTS. Pengaruh Lingkungan Kerja Dan Perilaku Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Pegawai. J Manajemen, Bisnis, dan Organ. 2018;
- [11] Mulyadi. Auditing. Edisi keen. Jakarta: Salemba Empat; 2014.
- [12] Zahra E. Pengaruh Integritas, Kompetensi dan Loyalitas kepemimpinan terhadap kepercayaan para bawahan di SBU perkapalan PT Pusri Palembang. J Ilm Orasi Bisnis. 2011;11((1)).
- [13] Wasim SMS, Ur Rehman M. Role of Transformational Leadership Style of Accounting Professionals towards Subordinates Performance, OCB, and Innovation: Mediating Effect of Integrity and Thriving. J Entrep Manag Innov. 2022;4(1):1–26.
- [14] Rani FKG, Lambey L, Pinatik S. Pengaruh Integritas, Kompetensi, Dan Profesionalisme Terhadap Produktivitas Kerja Karyawan Bagian Akuntansi Pada Pt. Bank Mandiri (Persero) Tbk Manado. Going Concern J Ris Akunt. 2018;13(04):41–51.
- [15] Arfah Salwa, Yuwaldi Away MT. Pengaruh Komitmen, Integritas Dan Kompetensi Terhadap Kinerja Komisi Pegawai Serta Dampaknya Pada Kinerja Independen Pemilihan (Kip) Aceh. J Magister Manaj Fak Ekon dan Bisnis Unsyiah. 2018;Vol 2(No 1).

- [16] Farah Humaira, Syahrums Agung EK. Pengaruh Integritas Dan Pengembangan Karir Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan. 2019;Vol 2(No 3). Available from: <http://ejournal.uikabogor.ac.id/index.php/Manager/inde>
- [17] Arman S. Pengaruh Independensi, Integritas, Budaya Kerja, Kecerdasan Emosional dan Gaya Kepemimpinan terhadap Kinerja Auditor Kantor Akuntan Publik (Kap) di Makassar. , 278-293. *J Ilm Akmen*. 2018;15((2)).
- [18] Yulianti L, Rasuli M, Oktari V. Pengaruh Integritas, Objektivitas Dan Kompetensi Terhadap Kinerja Auditor: Budaya Organisasi Sebagai Pemoderasi. *Curr J Kaji Akunt dan Bisnis Terkini*. 2020;1(3):347–62.
- [19] Davis, Keith dan John W. Newstrom. *Perilaku dalam Organisasi*. Jakarta: Gelora Aksara Pertama; 2001.
- [20] Wirawan. *Evaluasi Kinerja Sumber Daya Manusia Teori Aplikasi dan Penelitian*. Jakarta: Penerbit: Salemba Empat; 2009.
- [21] Pasaribu EK, Indrawati AD. Pengaruh Iklim Organisasi dan Kualitas Kehidupan Kerja terhadap Kinerja Pegawai Dinas Sosial Provinsi Bali. *E-Jurnal Manaj Univ Udayana*. 2016;5(12):254954.
- [22] Mishra, B., & Tikoria J. Impact of ethical leadership on organizational climate and its subsequent influence on job commitment: a study in hospital context. *J Manag Dev*. 2021;
- [23] Kurniawati E. Pengaruh Budaya Organisasi dan Iklim Organisasi terhadap Kinerja Pegawai. *J Dimens*. 2018;7((2)):240–54.
- [24] Triastuti DA. Pengaruh Lingkungan Kerja, Kompetensi Dan Iklim Organisasi Terhadap Kinerja Pegawai. *J Manag Rev*. 2019;2(2):203.
- [25] Khasanah DU, Apriliani R, ... Pengaruh Stres Kerja, Beban Kerja Dan Iklim Organisasi Terhadap Kepuasan Kerja Karyawan Cv. Cahaya Mustika Grabag Magelang *J Econ ... [Internet]*. 2019;1(1):16–23. Available from: <https://ojs.unsiq.ac.id/index.php/jebe/article/view/871>
- [26] Chandrasari F. Pengaruh Iklim Organisasi, Motivasi Dan Kedisiplinan Yang Diperkuat Oleh Skills Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan Lppks Indonesia. *JBTI J Bisnis Teor dan Implementasi*. 2017;8(2):145–60.
- [27] Sanjaya AKW, Zamzam F, Rostiati N. Pengaruh Iklim Organisasi, Pendidikan Dan Pelatihan Serta Komitmen Organisasi Terhadap Kinerja Auditor Pada Kantor Perwakilan Bpkp Provinsi Sumatera Selatan. *Integritas J Manaj Prof*. 2021;2(2):249–62.
- [28] John, S. dkk. *Perilaku Organisasional*. Yogyakarta. Sekolah Tinggi Ilmu Ekonomi YKPN; 2003.
- [29] Griffiths A. *Work organization and stress*. Switzerland: WHO; 2004.
- [30] Tarigan HG dan DT. *Pengajaran Analisis Kesalahan Berbahasa*. Bandung: Angkasa Bandung.; 2011.
- [31] Rai IGA. *Audit kinerja pada sektor publik: konsep, praktik, studi kasus*. Penerbit Salemba.; 2008.
- [32] Mulyadi. *Auditing. Buku 1*. Jakarta: Salemba Empat; 2002.
- [33] Luthans F. *Prilaku Organisasi. Edisi 10*. Yogyakarta: Penerbit Andi; 2006.
- [34] Putra KBSM, Suwandana IGM. Pengaruh Iklim Organisasi Terhadap Turnover Intention Dengan Kepuasan Kerja Sebagai Variabel Intervening. *E-Jurnal Manaj Unud*. 2017;6(5):2417–44.
- [35] Simamora H. *Manajemen sumber daya manusia*. 2004.
- [36] Tadampali, A. C. T., Hadi, A., & Salam R. Pengaruh iklim organisasi terhadap turnover intention melalui kepuasan kerja sebagai variabel intervening pada PT Bank Sulselbar. , , . *J Ilm Ilmu Adm Publik*. 2016;6((2)):35–46.
- [37] Kasmir. *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia (Teori dan Praktik)*. Depok: PT Rajagrafindo Persada; 2016.
- [38] Bintoro, D., & Daryanto D. *Manajemen penilaian kinerja karyawan*. Yogyakarta: Gava Media; 2017.
- [39] Mangkunegara AP, Agustine R. Effect of Training, Motivation and Work Environment on Physicians' Performance. *Acad J Interdiscip Stud*. 2016;5(1):173–88.
- [40] Sutrisno E. *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*. Jakarta: Kencana; 2016.
- [41] Veithzal Rivai. *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia Untuk Perusahaan Dari Teori Ke Praktek*. Bandung: Rajagrafindo persada; 2013.
- [42] PeraturanNo2-2018.pdf.